

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEGAL REGULATION OF CREDIT RELATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Credit, along with the introduction of innovations, entrepreneurial activity and stimulating state regulation of the economy, is one of the key factors that significantly ensure economic growth in any modern state. The effective organization of a loan is ensured, first of all, by the effective organization of its legal regulation - the publication by the authorized state bodies of the rules of conduct for participants in credit relations and ensuring their strict implementation. Understanding the social relations as fundamental condition for their effective legal regulation, we will briefly reveal the essence of modern credit relations.

term "credit" comes from the Latin words "creditum" - a loan and "credo" - I believe, I trust. Explanatory Dictionary of S.I. Ozhegova defines credit as a) a loan, the provision of valuables (money, goods, etc.) in debt and b) commercial trust. [one]

The concept of "credit" is the subject of an in-depth study by both economists and civil lawyers. Since the economic aspect of

ABSTRACT

Based on the provisions of the science of civil law, economics and civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this article analyzes the features of the legal regulation of credit relations, the main provisions of legal acts regulating the activities of participants in credit relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

credit is the content of credit relations and predetermines its legal aspect as the legal form of its implementation, we first consider the most generally accepted provisions of economic science in the field of credit.

In economic science, there are a significant number of definitions of the concept of "credit". However, scientists - economists are unanimous in the opinion that a loan should be understood as the provision of free material assets (money, goods, etc.) by some persons - creditors, or owners of temporarily free funds, to other persons - borrowers, or temporarily in need of them, on the terms repayment, urgency and payment. In particular, according to V.P. Klimovich credit should be considered as economic relations arising between the owners regarding the redistribution of temporarily free material and cash on the terms of payment and repayment. [2]

From the point of economic science, the essence of credit is most clearly expressed in its role, principles and functions.

The role of the loan is to ensure the temporary transfer of free funds of some economic agents to other, temporarily in need of them, economic agents. Linking the intensive development of credit with the emergence of industrial and commercial capital, V.M. Romanovsky notes that the circulation of industrial capital inevitably leads, on the one hand, to the emergence of temporarily free money capital, and, on the other hand, to the emergence of a temporary need for additional resources. Credit serves to resolve this contradiction. [3]

The main principles of the loan are its repayment, urgency and payment. According to L.I. Yuzovich, the principle of repayment is the main essential characteristic of a loan. It is direct repayment that distinguishes credit from other economic categories. [4] The principle of urgency of the loan means that it must be repaid within the time agreed by the parties - both the loan and the borrower in their plans take into account the repayment period of the loan and therefore it cannot be indefinite or until the moment of demand. The principle of payment means that the lender must receive, in addition to the loan, an additional material benefit, which can be either in monetary form or in kind - an additional supply of goods, etc.

Among the numerous functions of credit considered by scientists- economists, the author would like to note only three generally recognized of them - redistributive, accumulating and control. The redistributive function, according to the unanimous opinion of all representatives of economic science, is the main and meaning-forming function of credit - it is in this function that the essence

of credit is expressed: with its help, temporarily free resources of some subjects of economic relations are transferred to others, temporarily in need of them, subjects. The accumulating function of the loan allows you to form a financial basis for the expansion of production and other activities, providing the economic entity with financial resources in the required volumes. The control function of the loan consists in the implementation by the creditor of control over the targeted nature and efficiency of the use of the funds provided.

Legal scholars consider credit from the point of view of its legal essence, focusing primarily on the mutual rights and obligations of participants in credit relations.

Russian jurist A.P. Sergeev points to the mismatch of the concept of "credit" in the economic sense with a similar concept in law. [5] In his opinion, in civil law, the economic concept of "credit" corresponds to the terms "loan obligation" or "loan-credit relations", which, in addition to the traditional for the science of Civil law loan agreements, credit, commodity credit and commercial credit (loan relations in the narrow sense of the word), also include bank account agreements, bank deposit agreements and a financing agreement against the assignment of a monetary claim (loan relations in the broad sense of the word). According to V. Vitryansky, generic affiliation means the possibility of applying the rules on a loan agreement to other contracts if they do not have species-forming features or if there are no special rules, from which it is concluded that the loan agreement is a group-forming nature in relation to the above civil law contracts. [6]

The multifaceted economic activity of a person, aimed at meeting his ever-increasing needs, determines the diversity of credit relations - in pursuit of their commercial goals and in an effort to constantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of their activities, business entities seek to use new methods and ways of financing their activities. In order to streamline public credit relations, the legislator seeks to construct such legal forms that would preserve the nature of credit and at the same time reflect certain features of certain types of credit relations. Therefore, E.A. Sukhanov, pointing out that loan, credit and factoring agreements are agreements for granting a loan in the economic sense, argues that credit economic relations as economic intermediary relations can be formalized in different ways:

- in the form of loan agreements for money or things (goods);
- by issuing bonds;
- issuance of bills;
- novation (replacement) of debt into a monetary obligation;
- in the form of a credit (monetary) agreement;
- in the form of an agreement on the provision of a commodity loan;
- with the help of a commercial loan (prepayment, advance payment or deferral or installment payment provided to the counterparty under the contract);
- in the form of a factoring agreement. [7]

According to the author of this scientific article, the issue of legal regulation of credit relations should cover not only the implementation of a loan agreement (including a bank loan, a commercial loan and the provision of things on credit) and a loan agreement (including a loan in the

form of a bill, bonds, a state loan and innovations of other loan agreements), but also financing agreements against the assignment of a monetary claim, bank account agreements, bank deposit and leasing agreements. All of the above civil law agreements legally formalize the loan as an economic category.

Currently, the main legal form for the implementation of economic credit relations is a loan agreement. In any modern state, a loan agreement concluded by banks and other credit institutions with their borrowers legally mediates the bulk of the loan capital flow - in the Republic of Uzbekistan, bank lending accounts for more than 90% of commercial financing of the country's economy. Such a high percentage of the share of bank lending is due, among other things, to the underdevelopment of other forms of financing for business entities.

loan agreement is devoted to §2 of Chapter 41 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [8] Of the five articles of this paragraph, three (articles 744-746) are directly devoted to a loan in the strict sense of the word - a loan as an agreement between a bank or other credit institution to provide funds to a borrower on terms of maturity, payment and repayment. Articles 747 (agreement on the provision of things on credit) and 748 (commercial credit) are rarely applied in practice, since when concluding agreements on the provision of things on credit or on a commercial loan, the rules on the sale or relevant agreements mediating a commercial loan are applied - the possibility of applying such rules is provided for in these articles themselves. For example, leasing as a kind of commercial loan is regulated not only by §6 of Chapter 34 of the Civil Code of the

Republic of Uzbekistan, but by special legislation, in particular the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Leasing".

However, the small number of articles of this paragraph of Chapter 41, dedicated to the loan agreement, is compensated by the legal norm contained in the third part of Article 744 of this Code - the rules of § 1 of this Chapter apply to relations under the loan agreement, unless otherwise provided by the rules of this paragraph and does not follow from the essence loan agreement.

The legal norms governing economic credit relations are also contained in the following chapters of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, devoted to certain types of civil law contracts:

- Chapter 42: financing against the assignment of a monetary claim;
- Chapter 43: bank deposit;
- Chapter 44: bank account;
- §6 Chapter 34: leasing.

In addition, in the legal regulation of public credit relations, numerous norms of Part I of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan are applied. The most important for the legal regulation of credit relations are the rules contained in Section III - the law of obligations. In particular, the norms of the articles included in Chapters 21-23 and related to the fulfillment of obligations, securing the fulfillment of obligations, and liability for their violation are usually included in civil law agreements governing relations between the lender and the borrower - in loan agreements, agreements loan, pledge and guarantee agreements, etc.). [9]

Public credit relations are also governed by the rules of law contained in the law, adopted in accordance with the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of

Uzbekistan. The most commonly used in the field of legal regulation of credit relations are the following laws:

- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Pledge", the norms of which are applied in the notary execution of pledge agreements for vehicles; [10]
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Mortgage", the main requirements of which must be observed when notarizing a mortgage agreement for real estate; [11]
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Banks and Banking", the norms of which are applied when regulating the activities of banks acting as a creditor in credit, leasing agreements and when acquiring bonds and other securities, and as a borrower in bank deposit agreements, bank accounts and when issuing bonds and other securities, etc.; [12]
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Securities Market", which contains the rules governing the issuance, placement and circulation of securities (bonds, bills of exchange, certificates of deposit, etc.), through which the movement of credit resources from creditors - buyers of securities is carried out to borrowers - their issuers; [13]
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Leasing", the rules of which are applied in the implementation of leasing activities, i.e. when financing the acquisition by the lessor of equipment for the lessee and its transfer to temporary possession and use with the obligation of the lessee to reimburse the lessor's expenses and pay interest; [14]
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On consumer credit", the norms of which are applied when lending to the consumer needs of the population in the form of bank and commodity loans; [15]

Thus, public economic credit relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan are regulated mainly by the norms of the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, among which the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan takes the leading place. A loan as a set of economic relations for the temporary

provision of money and goods on a paid basis is regulated by Chapters 41-43 and §6 of Chapter 34, and, according to the author of this scientific article, consider a loan, bank and commercial credit, factoring and leasing, bank deposit and maintaining a bank account.

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